

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D14.4 – Project plan for optional services and future cooperation with IDDO

WP14 – Design, development, implementation and use of a repository for individual participant data from COVID-19 trials
Lead Beneficiary: ECRIN
WP co-leaders: Jacques Demotes (ECRIN), Gard Thomassen (UiO)

Authors of this deliverable: **Maria Panagiotopoulou (ECRIN), Maria Rujano (ECRIN), Gerd Felder (ECRIN), Sergio Contrino (ECRIN), Christian Ohmann (ECRIN), Swarnalathaa Kichenassamy (ECRIN), Sergei Gorianin (ECRIN), Jacques Demotes (ECRIN), Milen Kouylekov (UiO), Gard Thomassen (UiO), Philippe Guerin (IDDO), Mathew Brack (IDDO)**
With contributions from: **Jonathan Ewbank (ERINHA)**

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Executive Summary

In the context of EOSC-Life WP14, the collaboration between the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) and the University of Oslo (UiO) aims to jointly create, develop, implement, and maintain a Clinical Research Repository. This repository will host individual participant data (IPD) from COVID-19 clinical studies, adhering strictly to European regulations, especially the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The repository's functionality is divided between two primary systems: the Services for Sensitive Data (TSD) infrastructure managed by UiO and a Repository Management System (RMS) developed by ECRIN.

The RMS is purpose-built to facilitate and document the various workflows involved in managing the repository, including interactions with data object providers, requesters and users. The TSD system is responsible for securely storing, providing access to, and enabling the controlled reuse of data objects, such as datasets with restricted access.

The first chapter of this report provides a high-level description of the Clinical Research Repository workflows and operations with a focus given on the Data Transfer Process and the Data Use Process.

The second chapter describes the need for developing optional services to support the operations of the Clinical Research Repository. Gaps and needs in the current European clinical research data sharing landscape have been identified through a desktop search, discussion with stakeholders and a small-scale survey completed by people working in clinical trials and cohort studies. The authors of this report conclude that i) a de-identification support service, and ii) a data standards support service, would greatly assist data providers in making their clinical research data available for re-use, especially given that such expertise is often lacking in-house in academic settings.

The third chapter explores additional features that can be integrated to extend the core functionality of the Clinical Research Repository. A non-exhaustive list includes a file fingerprinting feature, a digital watermarking feature for (image) files, a summary statistics feature for dataset files and the provision of DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) reader and PACS (Picture Archiving and Communication Systems) within the secure TSD workspace.

The fourth chapter provides an assessment of the Infectious Diseases Data Observatory (IDDO), a data sharing platform established for malaria in 2009 and expanded on other infectious diseases since 2016 at the University of Oxford in the UK. More precisely, the EOSC-Life WP14 partners looked into the research themes covered by IDDO, the data transfer and data re-use processes, COVID-19-related work, collaboration with other repositories (e.g., Vivli) and FAIR registries (e.g., FAIRsharing). The aim of this assessment is to identify mutual points of interest and establish possible lines of future collaboration between IDDO and the Clinical Research Repository, for example as part of a common project proposal.

An overarching conclusion is that for these optional services, additional features, and plans for cooperation with IDDO to materialise, extensive discussion among the involved parties, funders and policy makers will be needed. The sustainability of the Clinical Research Repository for the next ~4 years has been secured via project funding, thus giving an opportunity for such dialogue to continue and project plans to evolve as needed.

Project Objectives

“D14.4 - Project plan for optional services and future cooperation with IDDO” contributed to the identification of gaps and needs in the current European landscape of clinical research data sharing and reuse. Feedback on gaps and needs was collected through a desktop search, surveys and workshops and it was used to inform the conception of two optional services and several additional features for extending the core functionality of the repository. In addition, this deliverable includes a detailed assessment of IDDO, its operations and workflows with the aim of identifying points of mutual interest for future cooperation with the EOSC-Life’s Clinical Research Repository.

The above serve the WP14 objective of defining the specifications, developing, implementing, and routinely operating a repository for IPD from COVID-19 trials, compliant with European regulations and in particular with GDPR, allowing clinical trial data sharing after completion of the trial.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Introduction

1.1 The Clinical Research Repository

The European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) and the University of Oslo (UiO) have already provided publicly available documentation to describe the Clinical Research Repository design¹, its technical implementation², first user feedback, maintenance and sustainability options³, and the repository data sharing policy⁴.

This section summarises information found in the previously provided documents with the aim to improve the independent readability of “D14.4 - Project plan for optional services and future cooperation with IDDO”.

The Clinical Research Repository is designed to provide secure, file-based storage for material generated by clinical research (e.g., cohort studies, clinical trials, observational studies), including documents, individual participant data (IPD) and metadata. This material is then made available for secondary use in accordance with the EU ethical and legal frameworks.

The EOSC-Life WP14 “Design, development, implementation and use of a repository for individual participant data from COVID-19 trials” kicked-off in March 2020 as part of the European Commission’s ERA vs. Corona Action Plan to help tackle the pandemic. As a result, the repository

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4141619>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6555207>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7836812>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5519121>

initially intends to store material from clinical studies related to COVID-19. Nevertheless, nothing inherent in the design or planned operation of the repository limits it to this particular research area. The stored material will remain as discrete files - there is no intention at this stage to aggregate data from different studies into a single platform, or curate data into a single structure. The repository is therefore similar in architecture to other file-based systems, e.g., Vivli⁵, CSDR⁶, and Dryad⁷.

The repository has been jointly designed and developed by ECRIN⁸ and UiO⁹. More precisely, UiO provides a pre-existing secure infrastructure for storage and access control, called TSD, for Services for Sensitive Data¹⁰. ECRIN acts as the main interface of the repository with the research community - i.e., negotiating with those providing the material and those requesting access to it, managing the processes of both data transfer and data use, ensuring the provision of adequate metadata, and monitoring compliance with legal and ethical obligations.

For clarity, some key terms used in this report are defined below:

A **Data Object** is any file available in electronic form, of any type (document, data, media, etc.). The repository will store and make available data objects, not simply “data” (or datasets, as defined below), because it is designed to contain protocols, analysis plans, consent forms, result summaries and other documents associated with a clinical research study, as well as IPD.

The term **Dataset** is used when referring to a data object that contains only data – e.g., a spreadsheet, CSV, JSON or XML file, database dump, etc. In the context of the repository, “dataset” will usually refer to the file or files of IPD derived from a clinical research study.

A Data Object Provider, or more often simply the **Provider**, is an organisation that provides data objects to the repository, i.e., that enters into a Data Transfer Agreement with the repository. Unless those data objects are already explicitly in the public domain, the Data Object Provider (e.g., a clinical trial sponsor) is assumed to have the legal power to enter into that agreement. For datasets of sensitive personal data, the Provider would be the data controller as defined under the EU GDPR.

Individuals seeking to re-use data objects are called Data Object Secondary Users, or simply the **Secondary Users**. The organisation arranging such re-use on their behalf, normally their employer, is the data object **Requester**. Figure 1 illustrates the roles of the various groups involved in the repository schematically.

⁵ <https://vivli.org/>

⁶ <https://www.clinicalstudydatarequest.com/>

⁷ <https://datadryad.org/stash/>

⁸ <https://ecrin.org/>

⁹ <https://www.uio.no/english/>

¹⁰ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

Figure 1: The main actors involved in the Clinical Research Repository.

The transfer of objects to the repository will be governed by a **Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)**, which covers the transfer of all data objects, including but not limited to datasets. Each DTA will include an appendix describing the data objects to be transferred to the repository, and the access arrangements desired for each of them. Further details (e.g., prerequisites for secondary use, categorisation as anonymised or pseudonymised) will be required for objects with restricted access. For data objects with restricted access, the Requester organisations will be asked to sign a **Data Use Agreement (DUA)** on behalf of the secondary users. The DUAs will constrain the use of the restricted access objects, typically explicitly prohibiting any attempt to re-identify individuals within a dataset, stipulating that datasets should be stored securely and destroyed after use, and requiring that the providers and repository are notified of the results of the secondary use. In some cases, providers may stipulate that access can only take place *in-situ*, within the TSD infrastructure. In the TSD Secure Processing Environment, commonly used data analysis software is pre-installed, including Amnesia¹¹, Gitea¹², R¹³, Stata¹⁴, Perl¹⁵, Python¹⁶ and SPSS¹⁷. Other software can be made available to users upon request.

The functionality of the repository is split between the Repository Management System (RMS)¹⁸, developed by ECRIN to support and record the workflows associated with managing the repository and its interactions with providers, users and requesters, and the TSD infrastructure

¹¹ <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

¹² <https://gitea.com/>

¹³ <https://www.r-project.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.stata.com/>

¹⁵ <https://www.perl.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.python.org/>

¹⁷ <https://www.ibm.com/spss>

¹⁸ <https://ecrin-rms.org/login>

which will be used for the secure storage, access and reuse of controlled-access data objects (e.g. datasets).

1.2 Functionality and workflows

As depicted in Figure 1, there are two main processes or workflows that the repository supports:

- the **Data Transfer Process (DTP)**, when clinical study material is provided to the repository.
- the **Data Use Process (DUP)**, when clinical study material is accessed for secondary use.

During the DTP:

- The initial information about the data objects to be uploaded, and the people who will upload them, will be collected within the RMS. This includes all the metadata pertinent to the study and the data object, as well as the access arrangements, as stipulated by the Providers, required for non-public data objects.
- Once this information has been collected a DTA can be drawn up (based on a standard template) and agreed, and this too is recorded in the RMS. The actual transfer can now take place: the RMS enables the data object transfer, shares with the TSD system the user information and TSD sets up the access modalities to the secure server.
- The user can upload, using the now active button in the RMS, the data object to the secure server in the TSD, where it will be stored in a dedicated secure space, organised according to a user/study/object structure.
- The TSD system alerts the RMS system when the upload is successful, and the RMS updates the state of the data object.

Figure 2: The Data Transfer Process.

During the DUP:

- Initial information about the request – including the data objects sought, the people requesting and the reasons for their request – is collected by ECRIN within the RMS. Where prerequisites have been established by the data providers, these are also checked.

- b) DUAs are established between the data requesters and either the data providers directly or between the requesters and the repository acting on behalf of the data providers (depending on the providers' previously stated preferences).
- c) Once the DUA is agreed the procedure is similar to the one for the DTP: the RMS enables the data object access, shares with the TSD system the user information and TSD sets up the 2-factor authentication for accessing the secure server. In this case also the specific permission of usage, for in-situ access and / or download, and an eventual time limit for access are provided.
- d) The TSD system alerts the RMS system when the access is successful.
- e) The RMS modifies the state of the data object revoking access, either when the access has been successful or when the time limit has expired.

Figure 3: The Data Use Process.

2. Need for optional services

Despite efforts from major stakeholders in the field to promote FAIR (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable*) clinical research data, in practice only a small percentage of studies make their data available for re-use. As an example, the percentage of clinical trials that state upon registration that they will make data available for sharing does not exceed 5-15% of the registered studies¹⁹, a percentage that drops even further when the principal investigators or sponsors are contacted with actual data sharing requests²⁰.

In 2018, Springer Nature published a whitepaper describing the practical challenges of researchers in data sharing²¹. According to a survey completed by 2,683 researchers working in medical sciences, the most often cited issue was *being unsure about copyright and licensing*

¹⁹ Larson K., Sim I., von Isenburg M. et al. (2022) COVID-19 interventional trials: Analysis of data sharing intentions during a time of pandemic. Contemporary Clinical Trials. 115:106709. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cct.2022.106709>

²⁰ Merson L., Ndwandwe D., Malinga T., Paparella G., Oneil K., Karam G., Terry R.F. (2022) Promotion of data sharing needs more than an emergency: An analysis of trends across clinical trials registered on the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform. Wellcome Open Research. 7:101. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17700.1>

²¹ <https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-research/open-data/practical-challenges-white-paper>

(44%), followed by *organising data in a way that is useful to others* (40%), *not knowing which repository to use* (37%), *lack of time* (25%) and *costs of sharing data* (21%).

Figure 4: Problems in sharing data in the medical sciences according to the Springer Nature survey, n=2683 (taken from 21).

A large number of “Other” issues reported by the respondents were related to data sensitivity (117 out of 172): “Ethical consideration, particularly participant’s confidentiality”, “Ethics and anonymisation of patient data”, “Privacy and ethics issues with clinical data”. In addition, de-identification of clinical research data for sharing can be time consuming and costly which might account for “cost” and “lack of time” being important limiting factors for medical researchers. These results support the findings of an earlier survey which demonstrated that the most common data sharing concerns of clinical researchers were related to “appropriate data use, investigator or funder interests, and protection of research subjects”²².

Within EOSC-Life WP14, ECRIN and UiO conducted on 23 June 2023 a smaller-scale survey (n=11) within our stakeholder community to identify remaining challenges for clinical research data sharing. The survey, carried out on Mentimeter, engaged a group of 11 respondents closely connected to clinical trials and cohort studies. These respondents, comprising roles such as project managers, trial managers, investigators, and statisticians, were requested to prioritise a list of 7 pre-identified challenges (from the literature), based on their perceived importance. The overall ranking results are provided by Mentimeter (using a points system commonly used for positional voting called “borda count”, where the item ranked first will get as many points as the total number of items in the question, and then descending) and displayed in Figure 5.

²² Rathi V., Dzara K., Gross C. P., Hrynaskiewicz I., Joffe S. et al. (2012) Sharing of clinical trial data among trialists: a cross sectional survey. *BMJ*. 345:e7570. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e7570>

Figure 5: Main challenges in sharing data from clinical trials and cohorts as reported in the ECRIN / UiO survey, n=11.

In alignment with the findings of the previous larger-scale surveys, our stakeholders consider uncertainties around ethical and legal issues the most important factor limiting clinical research data sharing. The second biggest challenge seems to be using data formats and standards (e.g., CDISC, OMOP) that make the data understandable and reusable by others. The respondents of the survey were aware of the Clinical Research Repository that ECRIN and UiO have developed and as such “*Not knowing which repository to use*” was not regarded as a major data sharing challenge. Nevertheless, there remain issues such as “*Fear of misuse and scooping*”, “*Costs of data sharing*”, “*Organisational policy & culture*” that will require policy changes from funders and publishers in order to be adequately addressed.

Based on the above, the following section describes 2 optional services that the Clinical Research Repository could design and implement to further support the clinical research community: i) A de-identification support service; ii) A data standards support service.

2.1 A de-identification support service

“Anonymisation” and “pseudonymisation” are two concepts covered by the GDPR. The former European 95/46/EC Data Protection Directive defined anonymous data as non-identifiable data and did not mention pseudonymised data, so data was either identifiable (personal) or non-identifiable data. The GDPR introduced a middle ground by formalising the notion of pseudonymised data.

Below, we provide some definitions of terms as used in this report.

Pseudonymised data: Personal data that has been processed in such a manner that it can no longer be attributed to a specific individual without having access to additional information (e.g., a data key), which is kept separately. Pseudonymised data is still considered personal data even if the actor processing the data does not have access to this additional information. [ref. Art. 4 GDPR]

Anonymous / anonymised data: Data that does not relate to an individual person or that has been irreversibly processed so that the individuals are no longer identifiable by the data controller or by another person. [ref. Rec. 26 GDPR]

De-identified data: Data where direct and indirect identifiers have been removed or generalised. The data may still be likely to reveal the individual’s identity, depending on the level of de-identification which has taken place.

In the U.S.A., clinical research data are covered by the U.S. Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). There are two de-identification standards specified in the HIPAA Privacy Rule: a) the Safe Harbor standard, and b) the statistical standard. The former standard is quite precise in that it specifies 18 data elements that must be removed (e.g., patient names, full dates, and full ZIP code) (Table 1). The latter standard requires that: a) a statistical expert performs the de-identification, b) the risk of re-identification is “very low”, and c) the de-identification method is documented. It's important to note that de-identified information under HIPAA is considered non-identifiable and is no longer subject to the requirements and restrictions of the HIPAA Privacy Rule. As such, it can be used for research and analysis²³. Nevertheless, it’s worth highlighting that **de-identification under HIPAA differs from anonymization under the EU GDPR** and “de-identified” data are not by default “GDPR anonymous”.

Table 1: The 18 elements in the HIPAA Privacy Rule Safe Harbor standard that must be removed or generalised for a dataset to be considered de-identified.

1	Names
2	All geographic subdivisions smaller than a State, including street address, city, county, precinct, zip code, and their equivalent geocodes, except for the initial three digits of a zip code if, according to the current publicly available data from the Bureau of the Census: (1) The geographic unit formed by combining all zip codes with the same three initial digits contains more than 20,000 people; and (2) The initial three digits of a zip code for all such geographic units containing 20,000 or fewer people is changed to 000.
3	All elements of dates (except year) for dates directly related to an individual, including birth date, admission date, discharge date, date of death; and all ages over 89 and all elements of dates (including year) indicative of such age, except that such ages and elements may be aggregated into a single category of age 90 or older.
4	Telephone numbers
5	Fax numbers
6	Electronic mail addresses
7	Social security numbers
8	Medical record numbers
9	Health plan beneficiary numbers
10	Account numbers

²³ El Emam K. (2011) Methods for the de-identification of electronic health records for genomic research. *Genome Med.* 3(4):25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/gm239>

11	Certificate/licence numbers
12	Vehicle identifiers and serial numbers, including licence plate numbers
13	Device identifiers and serial numbers
14	Web Universal Resource Locators (URLs)
15	Internet Protocol (IP) address numbers
16	Biometric identifiers, including finger and voice prints
17	Full face photographic images and any comparable images
18	Any other unique identifying number, characteristic, or code

In the EU, the GDPR does not directly provide a clear set of criteria to assess whether personal data is no longer identifiable and thus considered “anonymous” and outside of its scope. Important guidance on the topic of anonymisation techniques comes from the 95/46/EC Data Protection Directive Article 29 Working Party (WP29). This body, which has now become the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), issued an opinion aiming to address this issue. According to the WP29 2014 opinion on anonymisation techniques²⁴:

“Pseudonymisation consists of replacing one attribute (typically a unique attribute) in a record by another. The natural person is therefore still likely to be identified indirectly; accordingly, pseudonymisation when used alone will not result in an anonymous dataset [...] Pseudonymisation reduces the linkability of a dataset with the original identity of a data subject; as such, it is a useful security measure but not a method of anonymisation.”

“Thus, it is critical to understand that when a data controller does not delete the original (identifiable) data at event-level, and the data controller hands over part of this dataset (for example after removal or masking of identifiable data), the resulting dataset is still personal data. Only if the data controller would aggregate the data to a level where the individual events are no longer identifiable, the resulting dataset can be qualified as anonymous.”

The opinion highlights that “context” and “purpose” of anonymisation are important parameters to be taken into consideration. This means that the appropriate threshold of anonymisation is to be assessed on a case-by-case basis and by applying a “risk-based approach”.

An opinion, nevertheless, is not legally binding and in practice claiming that a dataset is “pseudonymised” or “anonymised” according to the GDPR has become a matter of interpretation by individual research groups.

Nowadays, a wide variety of so-called “privacy models” exist and are applied to personal health data²⁵:

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp216_en.pdf

²⁵ Sepas A., Bangash A.H., Alraoui O., El Emam K., El-Hussuna A. (2022). Algorithms to anonymize structured medical and healthcare data: A systematic review. Front Bioinform. 2:984807. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbinf.2022.984807>

- **k-Anonymity**: k-Anonymity is a privacy concept that aims to protect the identities of individuals in a dataset. It ensures that each individual in a released dataset cannot be distinguished or re-identified from at least k-1 other individuals. By generalising or suppressing certain attributes, the data is transformed to achieve the k-anonymity property.
- **ℓ-Diversity**: ℓ-Diversity builds upon the concept of k-anonymity by addressing attribute disclosure. It ensures that each group of records with the same identifying attributes (such as age or post code) contains at least ℓ well-represented values for sensitive attributes (such as race or medical conditions). This prevents adversaries from linking sensitive attributes to specific individuals within a group.
- **t-Closeness**: t-Closeness is another extension of k-anonymity that focuses on the distribution of sensitive attributes within each group. It ensures that the distribution of a sensitive attribute within a group is not significantly different from its distribution in the overall population. This prevents adversaries from inferring sensitive information based on the attribute values of a group.
- **δ-Disclosure Privacy**: δ-Disclosure privacy quantifies the amount of information or risk of disclosure associated with an individual record in a dataset. It represents the maximum allowed probability that an adversary can correctly determine the value of a sensitive attribute associated with a particular individual's record.
- **δ-Presence**: δ-Presence is a privacy concept that addresses the presence or absence of individuals in a dataset. It sets a threshold (δ) on the probability that an individual's presence can be inferred from the released data. If the probability exceeds δ , additional privacy protection measures, such as suppression or generalisation, are applied.
- **(k, ε)-Anonymity**: (k, ε)-Anonymity combines the concepts of k-anonymity and ε-differential privacy (see below). It ensures that a released dataset satisfies both properties. The parameter k denotes the minimum group size for k-anonymity, while ε quantifies the privacy budget or the maximum allowed privacy loss as per ε-differential privacy.
- **(h, k, p)-Coherence**: (h, k, p)-Coherence is a privacy concept that ensures consistency between the published data and the information available in public sources. It requires that the values of quasi-identifiers (attributes that can potentially identify individuals when combined) in the released dataset are coherent with the values available in public sources, up to a certain threshold h, to prevent re-identification attacks.
- **km-Anonymity**: km-Anonymity extends k-anonymity by considering the presence of background knowledge or external information that can potentially re-identify individuals. It aims to protect against attacks where an adversary combines the released data with external knowledge to breach privacy.
- **(k, km)-Anonymity**: (k, km)-Anonymity is a combination of k-anonymity and km-anonymity. It protects against re-identification attacks from adversaries possessing varying levels of background knowledge. It ensures that each group of records satisfies both k-anonymity (with respect to attributes within the dataset) and km-anonymity (with respect to external knowledge).
- **ε-Differential Privacy**: ε-Differential Privacy is a rigorous mathematical framework for quantifying privacy guarantees. It ensures that the inclusion or exclusion of an individual's data in a computation or analysis does not significantly affect the outcome, providing a level of privacy protection. The parameter ε controls the amount of privacy protection, with smaller values indicating stronger privacy guarantees.
- **(ε, δ)-Differential Privacy**: (ε, δ)-Differential Privacy is an extension of ε-differential privacy that offers a more fine-grained privacy guarantee. It provides bounds on both the ε parameter

(privacy loss) and the δ parameter (the probability of any additional privacy loss beyond ϵ). It allows for a controlled balance between privacy protection and utility.

However, it should be noted that secondary users have often questioned the utility for research purposes of data that has undergone extensive anonymisation techniques. Thus, the secondary research question is something that ideally should be taken into consideration when opting for one technique over another.

Developing a de-identification support service in the context of the Clinical Research Repository would need to be thoroughly discussed with stakeholders and funders but such a service could optionally include:

- **The development of a “De-identification Knowledge Base”**. This knowledge base would include information and training on the different anonymisation techniques and examples of practical application on dummy datasets. In addition, different anonymisation tools are now available, such as Amnesia²⁶, the ARX Data Anonymisation Tool²⁷, Anonimatron²⁸, μ -ARGUS²⁹, PRIVASA³⁰, Aircloak³¹. The service could provide information and training also on choosing the most appropriate tools and their use for de-identification of clinical research datasets. These tools can also be integrated in the TSD secure working space. If the owners of these anonymisation tools are willing to provide information and training material adapted to the needs of the clinical research community then this service could take the form of a “brokering” service between data providers and owners of anonymisation tools, facilitating the adaptation and use of such tools by the clinical research community.
- **The creation of a “De-identification Helpdesk”**. Depending on the resources available, a de-identification helpdesk could engage privacy experts to respond to questions of the repository users around the application of anonymisation techniques / the calculation of re-identification risks / the correct application of anonymisation tools.
- **A “Dataset De-identification service”**. Again, depending on the resources available, if researchers do not have the means within their institutions to perform the de-identification of their datasets, this could be delegated to privacy experts hired by the repository. This feature would require that there is an adequate legal basis for such processing to happen.

If there is mutual interest and funds available, the de-identification support service can be developed in collaboration with IDDO (see chapter 4).

2.2 A data standards support service

Data standards for interventional studies

Until approximately 15 years ago, there was a lack of uniformity in the structure and coding of result data in clinical trials, including commonly used data types like adverse events and medical

²⁶ <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

²⁷ <https://arx.deidentifier.org/>

²⁸ <https://realrolfje.github.io/anonimatron/>

²⁹ <https://research.cbs.nl/casc/mu.htm>

³⁰ <https://privasa.eu/>

³¹ <https://aircloak.com/>

history. As a result, there was minimal direct interoperability between datasets, hindering data exchange and integration.

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), however, faced with a bewildering array of datasets to assess, has been exerting increasing pressure to standardise the data submitted as part of a marketing authorisation. It now requires that such data are submitted, structured and coded using the CDISC Standard Data Tabulation Model (SDTM). The Japanese authority, the Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA), makes the same demand, and the use of SDTM is also preferred by the Chinese National Medical Products Administration (NMPA)³². The European Medicines Agency (EMA) has not yet set a similar requirement, but the relative importance of the U.S. market, at least for large pharmaceutical companies, has made the FDA requirement a powerful driver for increased standardisation in clinical trials data worldwide.

CDISC³³ (originally known as the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium, but now just as CDISC) originated in 1997 and became incorporated and funded, by its member organisations, from 2000. Though U.S. based, and with a close relationship to the FDA, it is global in scope. Over the past 20 years, CDISC has developed a wide range of standards and tools for different purposes (Figure 6).

Figure 6: CDISC data standards diagram expanded (taken from the CDISC website).

Among the various standards, SDTM and CDASH, both supporting syntactic and semantic standards, along with Define-XML, a standard for descriptive metadata, possess the highest potential for enhancing interoperability.

³² <https://www.cdisc.org/resources/global-regulatory-requirements>

³³ <https://www.cdisc.org/>

Table 2: Key CDISC Standards (available in the CDISC website to those with valid membership).

Name	Description/Use
SDTM	SDTM provides a standard for organising and formatting data in tables, to support data collection, management, analysis and reporting, data aggregation and warehousing, data mining, reuse and sharing, due diligence and other data review activities, and the regulatory approval process.
CDASH	CDASH establishes a standard way to collect data consistently across studies and sponsors, with data items then easily mapped to SDTM. This allows more transparency to regulators and others who conduct data review.
Define-XML	An extension of ODM-XML that structures metadata that describe any tabular dataset structure. It can be used with SDTM but is not restricted to that standard. It is also compatible with, and complementary to, Dataset-XML, a transport standard designed as a replacement for SAS V5 files.
ODM-XML	ODM-XML is designed for exchanging and archiving clinical data, along with their associated metadata, administrative data, reference data, and audit information.
ADaM	The Analysis Data Model, ADaM, defines dataset and metadata standards that support a) efficient generation, replication, and review of clinical trial statistical analyses, and b) traceability among analysis results, analysis data, and data represented in SDTM.
TAUGs	Therapeutic Area User Guides (TAUGs) demonstrate how standards can be applied to specific disease areas. They include disease-specific metadata, examples and guidance on implementing CDISC standards. The TAUGs are issued and revised on an ad-hoc basis (currently there are 49 available ³⁴).
CDISC CT	CDISC Controlled Terminology is the set of CDISC developed (or adopted) standard expressions/values used with data items within CDISC-defined datasets. Managed in collaboration with the U.S. National Cancer Institute's Enterprise Vocabulary Services. The CDISC CT is updated regularly and published quarterly.

The commercial sector of clinical research has been compelled to adopt data standards, leading pharmaceutical companies and their clinical research organisations (CROs) to make significant investments in personnel and systems to facilitate their implementation. While not all interventional studies require data transformation into SDTM, commercial entities now frequently collect study data using CDASH, which greatly simplifies the process of creating SDTM files when required.

The non-commercial sector has not experienced the same regulatory pressures or resource availability to drive a widespread adoption of data standards. While some university and hospital trials units have experimented with aspects of the CDASH standard, and a few have extensively implemented it, the uptake of CDISC standards in academic interventional research has generally been limited. Currently, there is a scarcity of empirical data regarding the usage of data standards

³⁴ <https://www.cdisc.org/standards/therapeutic-areas>

among non-commercial trial units, making any assessment largely anecdotal. Individual researchers who conduct studies independently, without the support of a trials unit, are even less likely to be aware of or utilise data standards from CDISC or other sources.

Data standards for observational studies

Data coming from observational studies (e.g. cohorts), registries or Real World Data sources (e.g. hospitals) are much less standardised than those coming from interventional research.

OHDSI³⁵, short for Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics and pronounced as "Odyssey," is a collaborative global network focused on improving human health through interdisciplinary open science. It boasts over 3000 collaborators from diverse fields including biomedical informatics, epidemiology, statistics, informatics, health policy, and clinical sciences across 80 countries.

The establishment of the OHDSI community traces back to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP), a public-private partnership in the US. OMOP aimed to investigate the appropriate utilisation of observational healthcare databases for assessing the effects of medical products. Recognizing the technical challenges associated with conducting research across disparate observational databases, whether in a centralised environment or a federated research network, the team developed the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM).

Figure 7: Overview of all tables in the OMOP CDM.

³⁵ <https://www.ohdsi.org/>

The OMOP CDM is a standardised data model that provides a common structure for organising and integrating data from various observational health databases. It allows researchers to represent and analyse health data consistently across different sources, such as Electronic Health Records (EHR), claims databases, and registries. The CDM standardises the structure, format, and terminology used to represent clinical and administrative data. OMOP promotes the use of standardised vocabularies, such as SNOMED CT³⁶, RxNorm³⁷, and LOINC³⁸, to ensure consistent representation of clinical concepts across databases. This allows for meaningful comparisons and aggregations of data from different sources.

Other relevant data standards and initiatives

The availability of numerous data standards and guidelines for standardisation varies depending on the specific study topics. Within the context of the Clinical Research Repository's operations, several initiatives may prove relevant. These include the ones listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Other relevant initiatives focusing on data standardisation in clinical research.

Name	Aim	Reference
Health Level 7 (HL7)	ANSI-accredited standards developing organisation dedicated to providing a comprehensive framework and related standards for the exchange, integration, sharing, and retrieval of electronic health information that supports clinical practice and the management, delivery and evaluation of health services.	https://www.hl7.org/
Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)	While GA4GH does not develop formal standards, it fosters the development and adoption of harmonised technical frameworks and guidelines that facilitate interoperability and secure sharing of genomic and health-related data. These are referred to as GA4GH standards, and they cover various aspects of genomic data sharing, such as data formats, APIs, consent	https://www.ga4gh.org/

³⁶ <https://www.snomed.org/>

³⁷ <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/research/umls/rxnorm/index.html>

³⁸ <https://loinc.org/>

	frameworks, and privacy/security protocols.	
Maelstrom Research	Maelstrom provides tools, resources, and methodologies to promote data harmonisation, integration, and interoperability in observational studies, including cohort studies. It hosts the Maelstrom Research Catalogue, a web-based platform that serves as a standardised centralised metadata repository of observational studies and cohorts. The Mica software developed by Maelstrom assists in the harmonisation process by facilitating the mapping and transformation of variables from various studies into a common data structure.	https://www.maelstrom-research.org/
Research Data Alliance (RDA)	RDA is a global organisation focused on facilitating the exchange and sharing of research data across disciplines and borders. While RDA does not develop formal standards, it fosters the development of community-driven guidelines, recommendations, and best practices for research data management and sharing (e.g. Data Management Plans, persistent identifiers, citation and attribution).	https://www.rd-alliance.org/

The data standards support service, in the context of the Clinical Research Repository, would again need to be thoroughly discussed and designed together with funders and key stakeholders but such a service could optionally include:

- **The development of a “Data standards Knowledge Base”**. This knowledge base would include information and training on the different data standards that are available to support better interoperability and harmonisation of clinical research data (e.g., on the application of CDISC, OMOP, guidance from GA4GH, RDA, Maelstrom etc.). When the relevant data standardisation bodies provide information and training material adapted to the needs of the clinical research community this service can take the form of a “brokering” service between

data providers and the data standardisation bodies, facilitating the application of standards by the clinical research community.

- **The creation of a “Data standards Helpdesk”**. Depending on the resources available and based on willingness of data standardisation communities (e.g., CDISC, OMOP, HL7) to collaborate, a data standards helpdesk could involve experts answering questions from repository users about the application of data standards / mappings between standards / harmonisation techniques to integrate data from different studies.
- **A “Data standards service”**. Depending on the available resources, if researchers lack the necessary means within their institutions to implement data standards, mappings, and harmonisation methods, the repository could consider engaging experts who offer these services. While implementing such a feature may require more resources, it would alleviate a significant burden from clinical researchers, allowing them to focus on their core responsibilities.

If there is mutual interest and funds available, the data standards support service can be developed in collaboration with IDDO (see chapter 4).

3. Need for additional features

3.1 A file fingerprinting feature

File fingerprinting (also known as file hashing or digital fingerprinting) is used to map data items such as computer files to a unique fixed-size string. Its main applications are data integrity validation (e.g., to check that a file transfer did not corrupt the original data) and file deduplication. In the context of the repository, we could integrate this additional feature in the TSD workspace to avoid sharing with users corrupted files or having file duplicates within the system. This can be a permanent feature of the repository and implemented using existing methods (e.g., MD5sum, SHA-256).

3.2 A digital watermarking feature for (image) files

Enabling digital watermarking for image files could be an interesting feature if data providers see the need for source tracking: for example, to verify that an image file downloaded from the repository is not reused beyond the agreed terms. Digital watermarking is mainly utilised in noise-tolerant signals, in particular it can be effectively used for images. If there is interest from the repository users, this feature could be provided as an option. Beyond image files, we could investigate if this technique is reasonably applicable to other types of files, for example by marking or altering the file descriptor.

3.3 A summary statistics feature for dataset files

This additional feature would aim to provide summary statistics for dataset files uploaded to the secure server of TSD. For example, it could summarise dimensions of the dataset (number of

columns and rows), number of missing values, statistical summaries for the various columns (e.g., average, min, max, standard deviation for numerical values, distribution of categories for categorical columns). If this is seen as useful by data providers or Secondary Users and the adequate legal basis is in place allowing for this processing to happen, then specific software libraries can be used and a programme creating summary statistics developed.

3.4 Provision of DICOM reader and PACS

DICOM³⁹ is the standard for the communication and management of medical imaging information and related data. It is most commonly used for storing and transmitting medical images enabling the integration of medical imaging devices such as scanners, servers, workstations, printers, network hardware, and PACS from multiple manufacturers. DICOM has gained significant adoption in hospitals and is increasingly being utilised in smaller healthcare settings, including dental clinics and doctors' offices. Since the repository may host an important volume of imaging data, it would be useful to provide in the TSD workspace a DICOM reader for viewing the files (with the capability to convert images from any source to a generic data format). For studies requiring the sharing of big volumes of images, the repository could also provide as an option an adequate archival system (e.g., similar to ^{40, 41}).

4. The Infectious Diseases Data Observatory (IDDO)

This chapter includes an assessment of the Infectious Diseases Data Observatory (IDDO)⁴² website, and publicly available documentation, performed by the EOSC-Life WP14 partners with the aim of identifying possible synergies between the two platforms.

IDDO is a collaborative data-sharing platform that facilitates the findability, accessibility and re-use of data for research and public health efforts related to emerging and neglected infectious diseases by providing the methods, governance and infrastructure to transform data into evidence and resources, enabling research-driven responses and improved patient outcomes worldwide. IDDO is committed to the active engagement of the communities most affected by such diseases in low- and middle-income countries.

Evolving from previous work of the WorldWide Antimalarial Resistance Network (WWARN)⁴³, IDDO launched in 2016 and is based in the Centre for Tropical Medicine and Global Health⁴⁴ at the University of Oxford, United Kingdom. Drawing upon WWARN's methods, structure and programmes, IDDO is applying the data sharing principles, processes and expertise developed for malaria, to a variety of infections and other neglected and emerging infectious diseases.

³⁹ <https://www.dicomstandard.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.santesoft.com/win/sante-free-pacs-server/sante-free-pacs-server.html>

⁴¹ <https://dicoogle.com/>

⁴² <https://www.iddo.org/>

⁴³ <https://www.wwarn.org/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.tropicalmedicine.ox.ac.uk/>

4.1 Research themes

According to the IDDO website, there are currently the following active areas of research work: **malaria, COVID-19, visceral leishmaniasis, medicine quality, schistosomiasis, soil-transmitted helminthiases, Ebola, Chagas disease** and **antimicrobial resistance**. More (e.g., HIV, melioidosis, mycetoma, scrub typhus, lymphatic filariasis) are being scoped for feasibility. The research themes covered are depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Research themes included in IDDO (taken from the IDDO website).

4.2 Data transfer and data re-use

A researcher who wishes to contribute data to IDDO, must first register, log in into the system and follow a simple process that includes:

- a) Name the dataset.
- b) Read and accept the terms of submission.
- c) Upload files in any format.
- d) Upload supporting information such as protocols, publications and data dictionaries.
- e) Add additional information such as details of any additional users the researcher would like to have access to the account, the PubMed ID if the dataset has been published, and any notes deemed useful to IDDO data managers.

The data will then be curated to the standardised platform structure to enable pooled analyses. IDDO has leveraged the accessibility, user friendliness and reproducibility of the SDTM standard to create a specialised IDDO CDISC Data Dictionary with a built-in implementation guide, specifically created for the aggregation of data for re-use. The Dictionary is disease-agnostic and covers a wide range of data types, allowing diverse data to be pooled for re-use in meta-analysis. With the addition of new data, new diseases and new data types, the Dictionary is iteratively expanding and developing⁴⁵.

⁴⁵ https://www.cdisc.org/sites/default/files/2021-05/CDISC_RWD_Connect_Report.pdf

Contributors may be contacted for further information regarding the dataset or be invited to form or join collaborative study groups. Data ownership remains with the data contributor, who will have no limitations on the use of their own data and have also the right to withdraw their data from the platform at any time. IDDO has no rights to the data and its role is limited to data curation and procuring access to data for research use only.

In terms of legal roles, the Data Contributors remain the data controllers, while IDDO is a data processor acting on behalf of the controller.

According to the IDDO website, the platform complies with UK and European laws and regulatory frameworks, in particular, but without limitation, these include rules and regulations governing the protection of personal data, clinical trials, research and the protection of human rights. The platform adheres to the UK Data Protection Act 2018⁴⁶, the EU GDPR and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁴⁷, an international agreement and cornerstone of international human rights law, protecting the individual right to privacy.

The data shared with IDDO through the IDDO secure upload portal are initially stored on a high-compliance server offering specific security features and limited access to selected administrators. All servers are hosted and controlled by the University of Oxford. Contributors depositing their data are asked to only share pseudonymised data (as defined by the GDPR). In addition to this request, an initial check is performed to remove any direct identifiers from the submitted dataset that may have accidentally been submitted before the data enter the curation workflow. IDDO follows the best practice established by the U.S. HIPAA Safe Harbour method of de-identification, where 16 of the 18 protected health identifiers as defined by HIPAA are removed (see Table 1).

Once HIPAA Safe Harbour is implemented, the submitted data then enters the curation workflow. Free text such as comments are examined for any identifying information and removed if found, which in effect is a thorough de-identification process. Date of birth is removed and only age retained. Country of data collection is retained. Institution names are provided to the data recipient (but not linked to individual patient data) for the purpose of appropriate participation and attribution of contributors. Upon completion of curation, the data is stored in a secure server.

Data domains within the available IDDO dataset are shared in a tailored manner according to the variables requested by the researcher. New patient keys will be generated using a random mechanism that will replace the original patient ID before externally sharing the database. This will ensure that multiple requests from the same research group will not be able to link the databases together.

Researchers are contractually obliged to not use, attempt to use or permit use of the dataset to re-identify any individual, community or medical institution associated with the dataset, nor link, attempt to link or permit a third Party to link the dataset with any other data in a manner that may enable re-identification of individuals, communities or medical institutions.

2) Accessing data⁴⁸

To access the data, the Data Requester must follow the following process:

⁴⁶ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1998/29/contents>

⁴⁷ <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/UDHR/Pages/Language.aspx?LangID=eng>

⁴⁸ <https://www.iddo.org/sites/default/files/publication/2023-02/IDDO%20Data%20Access%20Guidelines%2016JAN23.pdf>

- a) Complete a data access Application Form and list the requested data. No fees or other costs are applied following submission of the application form.
- b) IDDO works with the requester to ensure that the data access Application Form is complete before forwarding it to an independent Data Access Committee (DAC) for review.
- c) The DAC can decide to approve the application, approve with conditions (subject to the Data Requester obtaining funding and/or necessary approvals), reconsider the application (asking for further clarification or amendment by the Data Requester), or reject the application, if it doesn't meet the guidelines. Written justification will be provided by the DAC for rejected applications.
- d) Rejected applications and those for which amendments are requested will be reconsidered if the issues raised by the DAC are addressed in a revised application. Disputes and/or appeals regarding the data access decisions will be managed by the Chair or their delegate as appointed.
- e) A response from the DAC will be received in 2 weeks depending on the nature of the request. Research urgently required to respond to a public health emergency will, with the agreement of the DAC Chair, receive a response within 3 business days.
- f) All Data Recipients approved by the DAC to access Curated Data shall, as part of the terms of the DAC approval, invite the Data Contributor(s) to participate in the Proposed Research and/or to acknowledge Data Contributor(s) in the proposed research, as stipulated within the data use agreement.
- g) Data access applications must be amended if new members are added to the research team or if additional data is required.

4.3 IDDO and COVID-19

Since the scope of EOSC-Life WP14 is focused on COVID-19 research, the partners limited their assessment only to this disease area. According to the IDDO website⁴⁹ and in order to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic, partnerships have been developed with the following organisations and initiatives:

- **CDISC**⁵⁰: CDISC develops clinical data standards to improve the quality, documentation and integration of clinical data. The COVID-19 Interim Therapeutic Area User Guide⁵¹ and its associated tools were developed in partnership with IDDO.
- **COVID-19 Clinical Research Coalition**⁵²: IDDO is a founding member of the COVID-19 Clinical Research Coalition formed to build collaborative solutions and accelerate urgent research on prevention and diagnosis of COVID-19 in resource-limited settings. IDDO's Director, Professor Philippe Guérin, is a member of the COVID-19 Clinical Research Coalition steering committee. The coalition provides free access to COVID-19 clinical trial protocols⁵³.
- **CURE Drug Repurposing Collaboratory**⁵⁴: IDDO is closely working with CDRC, a public-private partnership led by the Critical Path Institute in collaboration with U.S. FDA and the National

⁴⁹ <https://www.iddo.org/covid19/about-us/our-covid-19-partners>

⁵⁰ <https://www.cdisc.org/>

⁵¹ <https://www.cdisc.org/standards/therapeutic-areas/covid-19>

⁵² <https://covid19crc.org/>

⁵³ <https://covid19crc.org/publications-and-resources/covid-19-studies/>

⁵⁴ <https://c-path.org/programs/cdrc/>

Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS) at the National Institutes of Health (NIH). CDRC builds upon the CURE ID⁵⁵ platform for drug repurposing for infectious diseases and is a key data contributor to IDDO's COVID-19 Data Platform.

- **Drugs for Neglected Diseases initiative:** IDDO is collaborating with DNDi's response⁵⁶ to the COVID-19 crisis. IDDO is also a partner in the ANTICOV⁵⁷ clinical trial platform.
- **Exaptive Cognitive City**⁵⁸: Exaptive's Cognitive City technology delivers the COVID-19 data platform inventory and the COVID-19 living systematic review interface.
- **Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network (GOARN)**⁵⁹: IDDO is also part of the WHO's GOARN network of over 250 technical institutions and networks globally that respond to acute public health events.
- **ISARIC**⁶⁰: The International Severe Acute Respiratory and emerging Infections Consortium (ISARIC) is a founding partner of IDDO's COVID-19 Data Platform. Large volumes of data available on the platform have resulted from ISARIC's collaboration of global researchers responding to COVID-19.
- **MORU Tropical Health Network:** IDDO shares its expertise with the ongoing COPCOV trial⁶¹ exploring how to protect those who work in healthcare settings.
- **RECOVERY trial:** IDDO is tasked by the RECOVERY international consortium to host and manage data sharing on its behalf⁶².
- **Society of Critical Care Medicine**⁶³: IDDO is collaborating with SCCM and their Discovery VIRUS COVID-19 Registry⁶⁴ partners as part of the CURE Drug Repurposing Collaboratory COVID-19 programme. SCCM is a significant contributor to the platform data and this collaboration will pool data from the EHRs of up to 300 sites from their VIRUS Registry to enable informed research into the repurposing of drugs to treat COVID-19.
- **TDR**⁶⁵: The WHO Special Programme for Research and Training in Tropical Diseases (TDR) chairs the COVID-19 Data Access Committee and supports IDDO to implement training and research capacity strengthening in lower-resource settings.
- **University of Cape Town (UCT)**⁶⁶: IDDO is working with UCT to support research to improve the treatment of COVID-19. UCT is also a member of the COVID-19 Clinical Research Coalition, and part of the working group Clinical Pharmacology & Drug Candidates which provides advice on clinical pharmacology, drug analysis, and clinical pharmacometrics relevant to COVID-19 clinical trials.
- **Vivli**⁶⁷: IDDO has made its COVID-19 studies discoverable on the Vivli platform to boost its reach across the global research community and increase both the speed of access and re-use of data. Vivli is also an individual participant-level data repository, sharing data from completed clinical trials to serve the international research community.

⁵⁵ <https://cure.ncats.io/home>

⁵⁶ <https://dndi.org/diseases/covid-19/>

⁵⁷ <https://anticov.org/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.exaptive.com/>

⁵⁹ <https://goarn.who.int/>

⁶⁰ <https://isaric.org/>

⁶¹ <https://www.tropmedres.ac/covid-19/copcov>

⁶² <https://www.recoverytrial.net/files/recovery-data-privacy-notice-v2-2-2021-11-10-1.pdf>

⁶³ <https://www.sccm.org/Home>

⁶⁴ <https://www.sccm.org/Research/Discovery-Research-Network/Discovery-Activities/VIRUS-COVID-19-Registry>

⁶⁵ <https://tdr.who.int/>

⁶⁶ <http://www.ccoat.uct.ac.za/>

⁶⁷ <https://vivli.org/>

IDDO has developed tools⁶⁸ aiming to make COVID-19 clinical research FAIR. One of them is the IDDO Cognitive City⁶⁹, a tool to view the types and volumes of data available, explore how the data can apply to the researcher's question and to request access to the data. Two things are available in the IDDO Cognitive city:

- A living systematic review of registered COVID-19 trials, currently including 14,942 studies performed in 160 countries. The metadata on the registered trials derives from the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP) and its source registries. Then, there is a substantial step of data curation and harmonisation of common terminology for searching by active pharmaceutical ingredients. The entire database is downloadable for further analysis and the content is updated on a monthly basis. The living systematic review presents some similarities with the ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository (MDR)⁷⁰, which collects and curates metadata from clinical trials and associated data objects from the following sources: ClinicalTrials.gov⁷¹, EUCTR⁷² (now CTIS), ISRCTN⁷³, WHO ICTRP⁷⁴, Pubmed⁷⁵, BioLINCC⁷⁶, YODA⁷⁷.
- The COVID-19 clinical data inventory which contains individual patient data. According to the IDDO website, the platform currently hosts data from 733,385 patients, from 37 countries. The majority of the COVID-19 data seems to come from the UK (272,560) and South Africa (428,124). With regards to the coverage of the European Economic Area (EEA), about 11,530 cases in total are included.

One difficulty that the EOSC-Life partners had when assessing the COVID-19 clinical data inventory was identifying whether the COVID-19 datasets come from EHR, observational studies or clinical trials. When datasets derive from observational studies or clinical trials it was also not possible to identify the studies that generated the dataset.

4.4 Findability of IDDO

IDDO has entries in the following catalogues to enhance its discoverability:

- FAIRsharing.org⁷⁸
- re3data.org⁷⁹

In October 2021, IDDO partnered with Vivli⁸⁰ as an action to help tackle the COVID-19 pandemic. IDDO enhanced the findability of their COVID-19 studies and associated data objects by providing

⁶⁸ <https://www.iddo.org/tools-researchers?page=1>

⁶⁹ <https://iddo.cognitive.city/cognitive/auth/landing>

⁷⁰ <https://crmdr.org/>

⁷¹ <https://clinicaltrials.gov/>

⁷² <https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/search>

⁷³ <https://www.isrctn.com/>

⁷⁴ <https://www.who.int/clinical-trials-registry-platform>

⁷⁵ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁷⁶ <https://biolincc.nhlbi.nih.gov/home/>

⁷⁷ <https://yoda.yale.edu/>

⁷⁸ <https://fairsharing.org/biodbcore-001473/>

⁷⁹ <https://fairsharing.org/biodbcore-001473/>

⁸⁰ <https://vivli.org/>

the metadata of these studies in the Vivli platform. This partnership covers only part of the IDDO data collection and is focused only on COVID-19. As stated in the Vivli member dedicated page⁸¹:

“The IDDO Data Platform hosts de-identified COVID-19 observational and clinical trial individual patient-level data and associated documentation. The metadata associated with these hosted datasets is searchable through the Vivli Platform. Once datasets of interest have been identified, approved users can receive data directly via the IDDO Data Platform. If researchers wish to upload IDDO data into the Vivli secure research environment to analyse with other data available only in Vivli, they may choose to do so.”

To access IDDO studies in Vivli, secondary users must follow the regular IDDO data access process. This means that they need to have a positive opinion from their independent Data Access Committee⁸² overseen by TDR. Approved applicants still need to agree to the IDDO Data Use Agreement⁸³ in order to access the data.

The screenshot shows the Vivli platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, About, Members, News & Events, Resources, and Find Studies. Below this is a search bar containing the text 'IDDO' and a 'CLOSE' button. The search results are displayed in a list format. On the left side, there are filters for 'STUDY DESIGN' (INTERVENTIONAL STUDIES, OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES), 'STUDY PHASE', 'SPONSOR INFORMATION' (SPONSOR TYPE, SPONSOR), and 'SAMPLE SIZE'. The main content area shows three study listings:

- Clinical Characterisation Protocol for Severe Emerging Infections**
IDs: NCT04262921 | C20-05
Condition or Disease: Coronavirus Infections
Intervention/treatment:
Buttons: Log in to Request Study, View Study Details
Number enrolled: -
- Clinical characterisation protocol for severe emerging infection**
IDs: ISRCTN66726260
Condition or Disease: Emerging Infections, COVID-19
Intervention/treatment: n/a
Buttons: Log in to Request Study, View Study Details
Number enrolled: -
- COVID-19 Critical Care Consortium Observational Study Incorporating the Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation for 2019 Novel Coronavirus Acute Respiratory Disease (ECMOCARD)**
IDs: ACTRN12620000421932
Condition or Disease: COVID-19
Intervention/treatment: n/a
Buttons: Log in to Request Study, View Study Details
Number enrolled: -

Figure 9: Results from a search in Vivli using “IDDO” as keyword.

⁸¹ <https://vivli.org/ourmember/iddo/>

⁸² <https://www.iddo.org/covid19/governance/covid-19-data-access-committee>

⁸³ <https://www.iddo.org/document/iddo-data-transfer-agreement>

4.5 Future cooperation with IDDO

IDDO would be a very valuable partner for the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository because of its substantial expertise in sharing data from emerging and neglected infectious diseases. The EOSC-Life WP14 partners held 3 bilateral meetings with the IDDO team (30 October 2020, 18 December 2020, 26 July 2023). IDDO had been identified early on as a key stakeholder for the Clinical Research Repository development and has been invited to attend the 2 Stakeholder Forum meetings that were organised within the project (7 & 11 December 2020-attended, 23 June 2023-not available).

Cooperation between the Clinical Research Repository and IDDO could focus on the following points:

- **Development and provision of de-identification services.** Such services are clearly needed, as researchers involved in clinical trials and cohort studies often do not have this expertise in-house. The two repositories could develop a joint de-identification service if this is desired by both parties or align their de-identification policies. IDDO has experience with data de-identification as part of the data standardisation process that can be leveraged for use cases requiring conversion of data to CDISC. For the rest of the studies in the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository, the de-identification service could take one of the forms described in chapter 2.1.
- **Development and provision of a data standards service.** IDDO has extensive experience with using CDISC SDTM for data curation. It would be advantageous for the scientific community (e.g., for meta-analysis experts) if the two repositories apply the same or a similar data curation model with the aim of enhancing their interoperability. In addition, IDDO is currently developing data transformation codes to transfer data from an SDTM to an ADaM compliant format. Not all the datasets coming into the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository need to be converted to CDISC standards, this could be offered as an ad-hoc optional service when the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository receives a relevant request from researchers working on a project that requires conversion to CDISC. As IDDO has already developed data standardisation capacities, there is no reason for duplicating efforts by developing an independent data standards service in the frame of the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository.
- It needs to be highlighted though that cooperation on implementing such a service is resource demanding. Data standardisation is a complicated process that is challenging to deliver across two different organisations (e.g., in terms of coordination, human resources and training required). In addition, it would require changes in the governance and legal documents (e.g., Data Transfer Agreements, Data Use Agreements) of both repositories to enable such data processing to occur and especially if this involves a data transfer from TSD to IDDO.
- In a similar way that IDDO cooperated with Vivli, the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository and IDDO **can share on each other's platforms metadata from the studies they hold and advertise them as available** to the users of both systems. This is the minimal level of collaboration expected.
- Currently IDDO has not implemented a Secure Processing Environment for *in-situ* analysis. Secondary users download the data, after signing a Data Use Agreement and can analyse them in their own machines. Although this is preferable by most secondary users, it might discourage some data providers based on liability concerns. For those data providers, IDDO and the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository could collaborate on an ad-hoc basis and

enable an *in-situ* reuse option in TSD, while the data use requests would be still dealt with by IDDO.

The current European data sharing landscape is rapidly evolving with the European Open Science Cloud and the European Health Data Space being two main actors pushing for FAIR clinical research data⁸⁴. Given the different developments and associated uncertainties, cooperation between the two repositories is reasonable for the following reasons:

- Brexit has had an impact on research collaborations between the UK and European countries, with the re-integration of the UK to the European research funding schemes still pending⁸⁵. In addition, data protection in the UK is no longer governed by the GDPR but by national law, the Data Protection Act 2018 (DPA 2018) and the UK has currently received an adequacy decision until 27 June 2025. Post-Brexit uncertainties may have an unpredictable impact on data providers based in the EEA who wish to transfer sensitive data in the UK. Until there is clarity and common agreements in place, it is likely that data providers and funders from the EEA (e.g., the EC, or national funding agencies such as the Agence Nationale de la Recherche-ANR in France) prefer that data generated from European funds are hosted within the EEA. This situation is undoubtedly hampering research and causing further fragmentation. A collaboration between the 2 repositories could ensure that data from clinical trials, observational studies and EHR continue to be shared while these uncertainties are being worked out.
- Currently, a proposal for the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation⁸⁶ is under discussion in the EU Parliament and Council. This regulation will cover the secondary use for research purposes of EHR, clinical trial data, cohort data and disease registry data among others. The proposal foresees that such secondary use will happen with authorisation from centralised Health Data Access Bodies in the Member States. This model creates additional uncertainties for the operations of centralised sensitive data repositories such as the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository and IDDO. Although the regulatory text may considerably change before implementation, an additional aspect to be considered will be the interplay between the EHDS and countries outside the EEA. A close collaboration between IDDO and the Clinical Research Repository would ensure better inclusion of both within the EHDS framework and avoid further fragmentation of the clinical research data sharing landscape.
- ECRIN currently has 11 Member countries (Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Poland, Spain, and Switzerland) and 1 Observer country (Slovakia). This means that it allows for a coverage of 349,000 European citizens. The network includes more than 120 Clinical Trial Units (CTUs) and ECRIN has certified 17 European Data Centers since 2014. In 2022, ECRIN supported 35 clinical trials. ECRIN aims to actively engage its network to address remaining data sharing challenges. Cooperation between the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository and IDDO has the potential to accelerate in the near future clinical trial data sharing and re-use in general and from the ECRIN member countries in particular. In addition, ECRIN has played an active role in enabling FAIR COVID-19 research via its involvement in the RDA COVID-19 working group focusing on clinical aspects⁸⁷.

⁸⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/7331832>

⁸⁵ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2023/jul/24/no-sign-of-deal-on-uk-return-to-eu-horizon-science-programme>

⁸⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0197>

⁸⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-covid19-clinical>

Figure 10: ECRIN member and observer countries (as of 19/07/2023)

- IDDO has long experience with data de-identification and data harmonisation with a big network of international actors engaged in the field of infectious diseases. In addition, IDDO has expertise in running individual patient data meta-analyses. Opting for complementary and interoperable systems would allow for more consistent data sharing and reuse, which is the goal of both platforms.

5. Conclusions and next steps

This report identifies relevant optional services and additional repository features that are likely to be useful to the users of the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository. A desktop search, several discussions with stakeholders and a short survey conducted by the EOSC-Life WP14 partners have led us to conclude that i) a de-identification support service, and ii) a data standards support service, will contribute to lifting remaining barriers to clinical research data sharing and re-use. This report also examines the workflows and operations of another data sharing platform established at the University of Oxford, the Infectious Diseases Data Observatory, in short IDDO. The aim of this assessment was to better understand each other's system and identify points of mutual interest between the two repositories in order to build interoperable and complementary solutions. Meetings with IDDO were organised in 2020, to serve as input to the design phase of the Clinical Research Repository and in 2023 to present to IDDO the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository alpha version and discuss possible common next steps.

The authors of this report strongly believe that a cooperation between the Clinical Research Repository and IDDO will enhance the visibility and use of both. With the EOSC-Life project coming to an end in August 2023, there are sustainability considerations that need to be addressed before this cooperation turns into a project plan. The Clinical Research Repository has

obtained resources through project funding for the next 4-5 years (e.g., through BY-COVID⁸⁸, canSERV⁸⁹ and a newly funded proposal as a response to INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06⁹⁰). The EOSC-Life WP14 partners plan in the following months to hold a discussion between ECRIN, TSD and the European Commission to see how the sustainable use of the Clinical Research Repository within the EEA can be enabled. Clinical research data sharing and re-use is still not seen as a common practice, rather the opposite, and policy makers and funders should provide the incentives to change the current situation. Data sharing comes with a cost that currently is not adequately budgeted through project funding (e.g., costs of long-term storage, costs of data de-identification or curation after completion of a research project).

Within the newly funded project under INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06, the Clinical Research Repository will start looking into requirements for interoperability with other health databases in cross-border settings. A project looking into better alignment and interoperability among IDDO, Vivli and the Clinical Research Repository would be beneficial to accelerate scientific breakthroughs through data sharing and reuse. Such an endeavour would also increase the cooperation between academia-driven clinical research (as represented by IDDO and the EOSC-Life Clinical Research Repository) and industry driven-clinical research (as represented by Vivli).

Abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
ADaM	Analysis Data Model (<i>CDISC standard</i>)
ANR	French National Research Agency (<i>Agence nationale de la recherche</i>)
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
API	Application Programming Interface
BioLINCC	Biologic Specimen and Data Repository Information Coordinating Center
CDASH	Clinical Data Acquisition Standards Harmonization (<i>CDISC</i>)
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
CDM	Common Data Model
CDRC	CURE Drug Repurposing Collaboratory
CRO	Contract Research Organisation

⁸⁸ <https://by-covid.org/>

⁸⁹ <https://www.canserv.eu/>

⁹⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2023-eosc-01-06>

CSDR	Clinical Study Data Request
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
CT	Controlled Terminology
CTIS	Clinical Trials Information System
CTU	Clinical Trials Unit
DAC	Data Access Committee
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DNDi	Drugs for Neglected Diseases initiative
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
DTP	Data Transfer Process
DUA	Data Use Agreement
DUP	Data Use Process
EC	European Commission
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EEA	European Economic Area
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
EUCTR	EU Clinical Trial Register
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDA	Food and Drug Administration (<i>U.S.A</i>)
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GOARN	Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (<i>U.S.A</i>)
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HL7	Health Level 7
ICTRP	International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (<i>WHO</i>)
IDDO	Infectious Diseases Data Observatory
IP	Internet Protocol
IPD	Individual Participant Data
ISARIC	International Severe Acute Respiratory and emerging Infections Consortium
ISRCTN	International Standard Randomised Controlled Trial Number (<i>Registry</i>)
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
MDR	ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository
NCATS	National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences
NIH	National Institutes of Health (<i>U.S.A</i>)
NMPA	National Medical Products Administration (<i>China</i>)
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication Systems
PMDA	Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (<i>Japan</i>)
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RMS	Repository Management System
RxNorm	Medical prescription normalised
SCCM	Society of Critical Care Medicine
SDTM	Study Data Tabulation Model (<i>CDISC</i>)

SNOMED CT	Systemised Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms
TAUG	Therapeutic Area User Guides (<i>CDISC</i>)
TDR	Special Programme for Research and Training in Tropical Diseases (<i>WHO</i>)
TSD	Trusted Signature Database (<i>a UiO service for sensitive data</i>)
UCT	University of Cape Town
UiO	University of Oslo
UK	United Kingdom
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
U.S.A.	United States of America
WWARN	WorldWide Antimalarial Resistance Network
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP29	The 95/46/EC Data Protection Directive Article 29 Working Party
YODA	Yale University Open Data Access
ZIP	Zone Improvement Plan

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery of “D14.4 - Project plan for optional services and future cooperation with IDDO” (initially foreseen in October 2022) has been delayed. The main reason for this is that the technical delivery of the Clinical Research Repository has taken longer than initially estimated. The delays are due to difficulties of ECRIN to recruit software engineers within the COVID-19 pandemic period and also due to unexpected technical issues with the integration of the Life Science AAI and the integration of the Repository Management System with the TSD secure infrastructure. As a result, most WP14 deliverables and milestones have been delayed.

Adjustments made

None

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